

WAU CONGRESS 2025

Antigua, Guatemala

Between utopia and the “current situation”: the possible university

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Fieldnotes...

14 February 2024

First day of fieldwork at UHo. The previous days had been particularly hard. Power cuts lasting up to 18 hours shaped every encounter. Yet, classes at UHo went on as usual. The classes in the Faculty of Social Sciences ran from 8:30 to 12:20, during which three subjects were taught. Classes had been shortened from 90 to 70 minutes to avoid teachers and students arriving late, due to the “current situation” of the transport...

Research question

What university is enacted when institutional life is continually reorganised through what teachers call 'current situation'?

Anthropology of Policy

Cris Shore and Susan Wright

- Policy as arena of meaning-making
- Policies are enacted and translated through practice
- Appropriation of policy (Gritt Nielsen)
- Policy as Cultural Text & Symbolic System

Methodology

- Fieldwork (2024): University of Holguín, eastern Cuba
- Five interviews – teachers of history and psychology

Cuban Higher Education Utopia

- Building a fairer society through education
 - Social transformation
 - Equity

Universal higher education

Ethnographic findings

“Current situation” and Adaptive Governance

- Defines what can and cannot be done
- Legitimises flexibility and discretion
- Creates moral consensus on what makes sense

- *“El problema del transporte cambia los horarios, el de la corriente cambia los planes de clase. — [Teacher 1]”*
- *“Ahora todo es relativo, porque uno tiene que resolver. — [Teacher 2]”*
- *“Cuando no hay transporte, se cambian los horarios, se recupera después... nadie te sanciona porque se entiende. — [Teacher 3]”*

Moral Commitment & Affective Communities

- Moral duty replaces material reward
- [Some] Departments operate through care, trust, and consensus
- Affective labour as governance mechanism
 - *“Esto espiritualmente ha sido mi segunda familia. — [Teacher 5]”*
 - *“Nosotros somos los que sostenemos la universidad desde el aula. — [Teacher 4]”*
 - *“Yo me quedo porque siento que formo parte de algo más grande. — [Teacher 2]”*

Between Utopia and the Possible

- Utopian past: expansion, purpose, equality
 - *“Fue un momento bonito... — [Teacher 5]”*
- ‘Current situation’: scarcity, fatigue, adaptation - [**Polycrisis**, Espina, 2024, 2025]

The Possible University — sustained through flexibility, care, affections and moral endurance

- *“Ahora trabajamos por sostener lo que queda. — [We used to work for an ideal, now we work to sustain what remains Teacher 4]”*

Conclusion

The Possible University

- Exists between utopia and current situation, in which current situation works as a *policy dispositive* that *authorises, legitimates and organises* university practices collectively.
- Is sustained by flexibility, consensus, and care
- Teachers enact the possible university through their everyday practices
- Teachers understand themselves as moral actors keeping the institution alive
 - *“If utopia was once a project of transformation, today it survives as a practice of endurance — quietly enacted every day by those who keep the university possible.”*